

INVESTIGATION OF POSTURAL CONTROL, FALL RISK, FUNCTIONAL MOBILITY, MANUAL DEXTERITY AND COGNITION OF PATIENTS WITH HEMIPLEGIA

Harun GENÇOSMANOĞLU^{1,5*}, Ayşe KURBAN², Hasan AKGÖL³ & Sevgi NAMA⁴

^{*1,2,3,4}Karabük University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Physiotherapy & Rehabilitation, Karabük, Türkiye.

⁵Hacettepe University, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Basic Physiotherapy & Rehabilitation, Ankara, Türkiye.

¹ORCID Code: 0000-0002-5258-8833

²ORCID Code: 0009-0007-7268-0198

³ORCID Code: 0009-0006-6743-5051

⁴ORCID Code: 0009-0008-9599-1922

ABSTRACT

Objective: To examine relationships between postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition in patients with hemiplegia and compare patients with right hemiplegia with patients with left hemiplegia. **Methods:** 51 patients with hemiplegia participated in the study. Manual dexterity, functional mobility, postural control, fall risk, and cognition were measured using the Grooved Pegboard Test, Timed Up and Go Test (TUG), Postural Assessment Scale for Stroke Patients, Performance-Oriented Mobility Assessment-1, and Montreal Cognitive Assessment, respectively. **Results:** No differences were between patients with right hemiplegia and patients with left hemiplegia ($p > .05$). Manual dexterity on the impaired side was correlated with manual dexterity on the healthy side ($\rho = .525, p = .025$), TUG ($\rho = .507, p = .028$), postural control ($\rho = -.623, p = .004$), but not correlated with cognition and fall risk ($p > .05$). Manual dexterity on the healthy side was correlated with TUG ($\rho = .371, p = .008$), postural control ($\rho = -.472, p < .001$), fall risk ($\rho = -.350, p = .013$), and cognition ($\rho = -.628, p < .001$). Postural control was correlated with TUG ($\rho = -.868, p < .001$), fall risk ($\rho = .940, p < .001$), and cognition ($\rho = .872, p < .001$). TUG was correlated with fall risk ($\rho = -.756, p < .001$) and cognition ($\rho = -.452, p < .001$). Fall risk was also correlated with cognition ($\rho = .855, p < .001$). **Conclusion:** All should be addressed holistically regardless of which side is impaired in patients with hemiplegia.

Keywords: Hemiplegia; Postural Control; Fall Risk; Functional Mobility; Manual Dexterity; Cognition

INTRODUCTION

Most stroke survivors experience a combination of loss of muscle strength, sensation, balance, cognition, and impairments in postural control and gait, leading to limitations in their ability to perform activities of daily living. Elderly individuals with stroke sequelae showed less postural control than healthy elderly individuals (Alfieri et al., 2016). A decrease in postural control has been observed towards the end of the first year following stroke (Persson et al., 2013). Impaired postural control is associated with older age, stroke severity, low physical activity before stroke, and use of neurotrophic drugs, especially opioids (Westerlind et al., 2019). It has also been shown that postural control observed in the first week after stroke onset is positively associated with physical activity level in the first year after stroke (Persson et al., 2016). Poor trunk control impacts balance and movement in stroke patients, increasing the risk of falls (Di Monaco et al., 2010). This explains why falls and poor balance are prevalent after a stroke (Persson et al., 2011; Tyson et al., 2006). Falls and poor balance have also been shown to affect the ability to walk and manage daily activities independently (Bohannon & Leary, 1995). Regarding cognition, recent research has shown that a sensory-cognitive-motor network system is required to recognize the appropriateness of a movement (Montero-Odasso et al., 2012; Park et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2021). Cognition is also associated with gait speed (Morris et al., 2016). Stroke patients with impaired cognitive function have lower balance and postural control, which increases their risk of falling while turning or sitting (Yu et al., 2021). Given the upper limb involvement, many studies have established that lower limb function influences postural balance and other factors, but few have demonstrated the role of the upper limb (Pijnappels et al., 2010). Motor function in the affected arm is substantially related to poor postural balance and functional mobility (Rafsten et al., 2019).

This study will contribute significantly to the literature by showing the influence of which body half was affected on postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition, as well as investigating the association between these features in patients with hemiplegia.

This study aimed to investigate postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition of patients with right hemiplegia to those with left hemiplegia and examine relationships between postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition in patients with hemiplegia.

The alternative hypotheses included in this study are as follows:

1. Patients with right hemiplegia have different postural control than those with left hemiplegia.
2. Patients with right hemiplegia have different fall risk than those with left hemiplegia.
3. Patients with right hemiplegia have different functional mobility than those with left hemiplegia.
4. Patients with right hemiplegia have different manual dexterity on the impaired side than those with left hemiplegia.
5. Patients with right hemiplegia have different manual dexterity on the healthy side than those with left hemiplegia.
6. Patients with right hemiplegia have different cognition than those with left hemiplegia.
7. Postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition are correlated in patients with right hemiplegia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a cross-sectional study. It was conducted at the Training and Research Center for Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation of Karabük University. Fifty-one hemiplegic patients who applied to special education and rehabilitation facilities in Karabük were referred to the center. Patients provided an informed consent form. The study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki on Medical Protocol and Ethics. The clinical research ethics committee of Kastamonu University approved this study. (Date: November 1, 2023, Number: 2023-KAEK-125).

The study comprised patients aged 18 to 65 with hemiplegia, a stable general condition, Turkish literacy, communication skills, and the ability to walk with an assistive device or entirely independently.

Patients with the following features were excluded from this study: (1) twice or more strokes, (2) bilateral hemiplegia, (3) tetraplegia, (4) quadriplegia, (5) breastfeeding, (6) pregnancy, (7) general anesthesia or surgery within the last six months, (8) intensive care within the last six months, and (9) any systemic disease such as neurological, psychiatric, immunological, rheumatological, oncological, etc. that may affect the evaluation.

Measurements

Manual dexterity was assessed with the Grooved Pegboard Test (Hung et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2016). Using one hand, participants were instructed to place the pegs on the board in a specific order and the correct direction. They were asked to complete the task as soon as possible. The test was performed with the unaffected and affected hands, respectively. The time taken for each hand was recorded in seconds. The test was performed twice, and the completion time was taken as the average of these two trials.

Functional mobility was assessed with the Timed Up and Go Test (Hafsteinsdottir et al., 2014; Podsiadlo & Richardson, 1991). The test evaluates the time it takes for a person to stand up from an ordinary chair approximately 46 cm high, walk 3 meters, turn 180°, walk back towards the chair, and sit down. The test was performed once before timing began to familiarize the person with the assessment. A stopwatch was used to measure performance.

Postural control was assessed using the Postural Assessment Scale for Stroke Patients (Koçak et al., 2019). The scale has twelve items with increasing difficulty. It is graded on a four-point scale (0: lowest to 3: highest). The scale scores range from 0 to 36.

Fall risk was assessed with the Performance-Oriented Mobility Assessment-1 (Yücel et al., 2012). The items are scored between 0-1 or 0-2. With a total of 17 items, a maximum total score of 28 can be obtained. An increase in the total score indicates a better performance; the lower the score, the higher the risk of falling.

Cognition was examined with the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Ozdilek & Kenangil, 2014). The scale score varies between 0 and 30. The scale score is calculated by summing the section scores. A decrease in the scale score indicates a reduction in cognitive level.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed in Jamovi version 2.3.21. The statistical significance was accepted as $p < .05$. The assumption of normal distribution was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test. Between-group analysis was made using the student's t-test or the Mann-Whitney U test. Spearman's correlation coefficient was used to conduct correlation analysis. The following rules were applied to interpret the

size of a correlation coefficient: value .00–.29 as negligible correlation, .30–.50 as low, .51–.70 as moderate, .71–.90 as high, and .91– 1.00 as very high correlation (Mukaka, 2012).

RESULTS

There were no differences between patients with right and left hemiplegia ($p > .05$) (Table 1).

Table 1. Between-group analysis

Measure	Statistic	P-value
<i>Manual dexterity (healthy)</i>	Mann-Whitney U = 264.0	0.432
<i>Manual dexterity (impaired)</i>	Mann-Whitney U = 43.0	0.905
<i>Functional mobility</i>	Mann-Whitney U = 222.0	0.066
<i>Postural control</i>	Mann-Whitney U = 235.5	0.113
<i>Fall risk</i>	Mann-Whitney U = 275.0	0.406
<i>Cognition</i>	Student's t = -0.862	0.393

Manual dexterity on the impaired side was associated with manual dexterity on the healthy side ($\rho = .525$, $p = .025$), functional mobility ($\rho = .507$, $p = .028$), and postural control ($\rho = -.623$, $p = .004$), but not with cognition or fall risk ($p > .05$). Functional mobility ($\rho = .371$, $p = .008$), postural control ($\rho = -.472$, $p < .001$), fall risk ($\rho = -.350$, $p = .013$), and cognition ($\rho = -.628$, $p < .001$) all showed a correlation with manual dexterity on the healthy side. Postural control was associated with functional mobility ($\rho = -.868$, $p < .001$), fall risk ($\rho = .940$, $p < .001$), and cognition ($\rho = .872$, $p < .001$). Functional mobility was associated with fall risk ($\rho = -.756$, $p < .001$) and cognition ($\rho = -.452$, $p < .001$). Fall risk was also correlated with cognition ($\rho = .855$, $p < .001$). (Table 2)

Table 2. Correlation analysis

Measure	<i>Manual dexterity (healthy)</i>	<i>Manual dexterity (impaired)</i>	<i>Functional mobility</i>	<i>Postural control</i>	<i>Fall risk</i>
<i>Manual dexterity (impaired)</i>	$\rho = .525$ $p = .025^*$				
<i>Functional mobility</i>	$\rho = .371$ $p = .008^*$	$\rho = .507$ $p = .028^*$			
<i>Postural control</i>	$\rho = -.472$ $p < .001^*$	$\rho = -.623$ $p = .004^*$	$\rho = -.868$ $p < .001^*$		
<i>Fall risk</i>	$\rho = -.350$ $p = .013^*$	$\rho = -.395$ $p = .095$	$\rho = -.756$ $p < .001^*$	$\rho = .940$ $p < .001^*$	
<i>Cognition</i>	$\rho = -.628$ $p < .001^*$	$\rho = -.430$ $p = .066$	$\rho = -.452$ $p < .001^*$	$\rho = .872$ $p < .001^*$	$\rho = .855$ $p < .001^*$

*: $p < .05$; ρ : Spearman's correlation coefficient

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to compare postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition in patients with right and left hemiplegia, as well as to examine relationships between postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition in patients with hemiplegia. Patients with right hemiplegia were similar to those with left hemiplegia in postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition. A very high correlation was shown between postural control and fall risk. A high correlation was demonstrated between postural control and functional mobility, postural control and cognition, functional mobility and fall risk, and fall risk and cognition. A moderate correlation was found between impaired and healthy side dexterity, and impaired side dexterity and functional mobility, impaired side dexterity and postural control, and healthy side dexterity and cognition. A low correlation was observed between healthy side dexterity and functional mobility, healthy side dexterity and postural control, healthy side dexterity and fall risk, and functional mobility and cognition.

There are some limitations in this study. First, a larger sample size is required for a normal data distribution. Second, analyses were not conducted for specific subsections of measurements. Thirdly, correlation analyses were not performed on patients with right or left hemiplegia. Fourthly, the time spent on the condition should have been considered. Lastly, the duration of previous rehabilitation was not taken into consideration.

CONCLUSION

Several correlations were found between postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, and cognition. Patients with right hemiplegia did not have different postural control, fall risk, functional mobility, manual dexterity, or cognition than those with left hemiplegia and vice versa. All features should be addressed holistically regardless of which side is impaired in patients with hemiplegia.

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